

THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CORPORATE TRAINING PLAN BASED ON INTERACTIVE METHODOLOGIES FOR PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCY DEVELOPMENT

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20576517

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to develop a corporate training plan grounded in interactive methodologies to enhance the professional competencies of industrial operators. In light of rapid labor-market transformations and increasing organizational investments in Training and Development (T&D), there is a growing need for more participatory training practices aligned with real organizational demands. The research adopts a qualitative, descriptive approach, developed through a case study conducted in a metal-mechanical company in the Serra Gaúcha region, involving 128 operators distributed across eight

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**Revista *OWL Journal*, Campina Grande - PB, v. 4 n. 6 (2026) - DOSSIÊ ESPECIAL:
Conhecimento, Formação e Transformação Social**

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groups. The training analyzed involved applying the “Box Game” dynamic, a practical simulation of a production line based on Lean Manufacturing principles. The activity was structured in progressive rounds that stimulated competencies such as collaboration, effective communication, problem-solving, critical thinking, planning, and resilience. The results demonstrated that interactive methodologies promote greater engagement, facilitate the assimilation of concepts, and improve production performance, while also strengthening a culture of continuous improvement. As the main outcome of this study, a training plan and a training manual were developed, with potential for replication in other organizations. It is concluded that interactive methodologies represent an effective alternative to traditional teaching models, enhancing meaningful learning and fostering both human and organizational development.

Keywords: interactive methodologies; corporate training; professional competencies.

1. INTRODUCTION

Constant transformations in the labor market, driven by globalization, digitalization, and advances in technology, have required organizations to become more adaptable. In this context, investing in the training and continuous development of teams has shifted from a competitive advantage to a strategic necessity for maintaining competitiveness.

According to the Brazilian Association for Training and Development (ABTD), in the 19th edition of the *Panorama of Training in Brazil*, it was found that in 2024 the average investment in Training and Development (T&D) per employee in the country increased by 14% compared to the previous year, reaching 24 hours of annual training per employee and surpassing, for the first time, the average recorded in the United States.

In this scenario, it is essential to recognize the strategic role of T&D not only as a qualification practice but also as a key instrument for competency development. This process prepares professionals to face organizational challenges and deliver high-quality results (Silva; Soares, 2020).

From this perspective, the *Future of Jobs Report* (World Economic Forum, 2025) indicates that approximately 39% of the competencies employers consider essential are expected to undergo transformation by 2030. Among these, analytical thinking, resilience,

leadership, creativity, curiosity, and continuous learning stand out. However, such skills are rarely fully developed through traditional training methods.

In this context, interactive methodologies gain relevance, as they emphasize practical experience, reflection, and participant engagement. By promoting greater active participation and collaboration, these methodologies emerge as effective alternatives to enhance learning and, consequently, the development of professional competencies in corporate environments.

Given these transformations and the growing recognition of human capital within organizations, it becomes relevant to question how interactive methodologies can effectively contribute to learning processes in corporate training. Thus, the research problem guiding this study is: *How can a corporate training plan, grounded in interactive methodologies, be developed to effectively contribute to the professional competency development of operators?*

Based on this question, the general objective of this study is to develop a corporate training plan with practical application potential, using interactive methodologies to develop operators' professional competencies.

To achieve this, the following specific objectives were defined: (i) to examine the effects of interactive methodologies on knowledge assimilation and retention; (ii) to investigate the contribution of these methodologies to the development of technical and behavioral skills; and (iii) to analyze the influence of interactive methodologies on collaboration, communication, and teamwork.

The relevance of this research lies in the need to understand how pedagogical practices grounded in interactive methodologies can enhance outcomes in both corporate settings and vocational education. In addition to addressing the demand for more prepared, engaged, and adaptable operators, adopting teaching strategies that emphasize active and reflective participation also strengthens teaching practices by aligning training processes with the evolving demands of the labor market and contemporary professional education methodologies.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In 1973, psychologist David McClelland published the article *Testing for Competence rather than Intelligence*, initiating discussions on competence among psychologists and management scholars. According to McClelland, competence is not something immediately visible, but rather an internal characteristic of an individual who performs a given task with superior performance. This characteristic may include knowledge, skills, attitudes, personality traits, motives, or patterns of thinking that consistently lead to effective results (McClelland, 1973).

During the 1980s, psychologist and former student of McClelland, Richard Boyatzis, continued these studies and further explored McClelland's concept of competence, particularly applying it to human resource management and organizational development. He identified a set of characteristics and traits that, in his view, define superior performance (Fleury; Fleury, 2001).

From this perspective, competence is understood as the integration of knowledge, skills, and attitudes—that is, a set of human capabilities that explain high levels of performance. It is assumed that excellence in performance is associated with attributes such as intelligence and personality traits. Thus, competence is viewed as a set of resources that individuals possess and mobilize in different contexts. Although the analysis focuses on the individual level, much of the North American literature emphasizes the need to align competencies with the specific requirements of roles or positions within organizations (Fleury; Fleury, 2001).

Guy Le Boterf (2003) deepens this understanding by proposing that individual competence is formed by three pillars. The first pillar, biography and socialization, encompasses an individual's life experiences, including values, beliefs, sociocultural experiences, and the environment in which they were raised. The second pillar, educational background, consists of the knowledge, skills, and learning acquired through formal and

informal educational processes. Finally, the third pillar, professional experience, is related to practices and experiences in the workplace, where individuals apply and refine their knowledge. The combination of these pillars forms a set of internal resources that individuals mobilize to act effectively in response to real demands and situations, thus revealing the dynamic and constructed nature of competence.

Le Boterf (2003) further emphasizes that competence is not merely about possessing knowledge, but about knowing how to apply it in the appropriate context, considering both internal resources (knowledge, skills, experiences, and personal traits) and external resources (available tools and means).

In this line of thought, Kilimnik, Sant'Anna, and Luz (2004) add that competence can be understood as the integration of multiple forms of knowledge acquired through different means, such as transfer, learning, and adaptation, which enable individuals to build a solid foundation of knowledge and skills aimed at solving problems in real contexts.

Based on these conceptions, Bruno-Faria and Brandão (2003) extend the analysis beyond the individual level and recognize that competencies may also encompass organizational levels. They define competence as a professional attribute capable of enabling the achievement of strategic objectives, ensuring competitive advantage, and generating benefits. The authors classify competencies into professional (those related to individuals or work teams) and organizational (those that characterize the organization as a whole), emphasizing that sustaining organizational competencies requires the support of professional competencies combined with other resources.

In view of these demands, the development of professional competencies requires strategies that go beyond initial academic training and incorporate continuous training activities. In this regard, several organizations have invested in structured training programs, such as corporate universities, aimed at both internal audiences and the broader community, seeking to align technical and behavioral skills with production demands. These initiatives demonstrate that training not only strengthens individual competencies but also contributes to

consolidating organizational competencies, enhancing innovation capacity and competitive advantage (Lazzareschi, 2018).

In a context of rapid transformations, technological innovation, and intense competition among organizations, companies have come to recognize that human capital is a key source of competitive advantage, requiring continuous initiatives to develop competencies (Dutra, 2006; Chiavenato, 2014). In this scenario, traditional education is no longer sufficient, and organizations have increasingly directed efforts toward more dynamic learning actions aligned with market demands (Silveira, 2021).

In this context, Training and Development (T&D) programs have been consolidated as strategic instruments to promote competencies aligned with organizational objectives. According to Silveira (2021), corporate training performs multiple functions: in addition to strengthening organizational culture and engaging operators, it directly supports strategic planning and the maintenance of competitive advantage. However, the effectiveness of these actions depends on adopting a systematic approach that includes needs assessment, a clear definition of objectives, an appropriate selection of pedagogical methods, and continuous evaluation of results.

As highlighted by Azeredo (2019), the pursuit of valuing internal talent has led many companies to invest continuously in training programs. However, the author warns that many of these initiatives fail to achieve the expected results, either because they fall short in diagnosing operators' real needs or because they lack continuity and integration with other management practices. This observation underscores the importance of treating training not as an isolated event, but as part of a broader organizational strategy.

In the same vein, Ceccon (2013, as cited in Azeredo, 2019) reinforces that training is one of the main tools used in the organizational development process. It contributes not only to improving individuals' technical and functional performance but also to strengthening interpersonal relationships and increasing productivity in the workplace.

According to Maués Filho et al. (2023), corporate training is a systematic, structured process aimed at developing skills, attitudes, and knowledge. Its main objective is to prepare individuals for the demands of their professional roles, enhancing performance, promoting talent retention, and optimizing the organization's human capital.

Thus, corporate training constitutes a fundamental component in the development of professional competencies. When strategically planned and supported by appropriate methodologies, such training programs have the potential to promote meaningful learning that can be applied to daily work activities (Maués Filho et al., 2023; Ceccon, 2013, as cited in Azeredo, 2019). This effectiveness becomes even more evident when training incorporates participatory approaches that increase operators' engagement and facilitate the practical application of acquired knowledge (Bruno-Faria & Brandão, 2003).

According to Santos and Costa (2019, as cited in Lúcio, Silva, Bonifácio, & Fernandes, 2025), continuous training is a systematic, ongoing process of acquiring knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable individuals and teams to adapt to change and face new challenges. Unlike traditional training models, which are punctual and focused on immediate needs, continuous training aims to foster a culture of continuous learning, which is essential in a dynamic, competitive market.

Organizations face increasing pressures, both from the external environment and from their internal work relationships, to invest in human development. In this sense, it becomes evident that stimulating and supporting the continuous improvement of operators is essential to preserving and enhancing competitive advantage. At the same time, individuals also pursue continuous development to ensure greater security, adaptability, and employability in response to labor market demands (Azeredo, 2019).

One way to deliver corporate training, according to Andrade (1999, as cited in Santos, Lázaro, & Sales, 2019), is through group dynamics, understood as a technique that provides practical experiences to a group of individuals, using games, exercises, and activities as tools to stimulate authenticity and individual development. Through these experiences, operators

can identify and value their own competencies and characteristics, thereby strengthening their role in organizational development.

Complementarily, Militão (2000, as cited in Santos, Lázaro, Sales, 2019) highlights that any group-based activity—such as meetings, workshops, training sessions, or large events—can be considered a group dynamic, as long as its purpose is to integrate, encourage participation, promote reflection, foster learning, or enhance interaction among participants.

Within this context, Perpétuo and Gonçalves (2005, as cited in Alberti et al., 2014) emphasize that group dynamics is an essential tool in education, as it can facilitate the teaching and learning process, especially when aiming to balance theory and practice. Furthermore, this approach recognizes all participants as active subjects and values their involvement in the educational process.

In this way, learning occurs collectively, with interaction among individuals fostering the shared construction of knowledge, stimulating creativity, enhancing participants' confidence, and contributing to improved productivity. Furthermore, it enables the recognition of possibilities for transformation, encourages teamwork, and strengthens both interpersonal and intrapersonal relationships, offering pathways to intervene in and modify reality. In technical courses in business administration, this approach is particularly relevant, as it seeks to promote the acquisition of new behaviors and competencies to efficiently develop human resource management processes (Alberti et al., 2014).

Lean Manufacturing originated in Japan, based on Toyota's experience after World War II. Faced with the challenge of rebuilding its factories, the company developed a production system that reduced waste, defects, and inventory while maintaining efficiency and product variety (Ikeziri et al., 2019). Taiichi Ohno and Shigeo Shingo integrated the concept of Just-in-Time with respect for people, giving rise to a more participatory, organized way of working that marked the beginning of the modern Lean philosophy.

The application of Lean Manufacturing relies on essential principles such as the pull system, cellular manufacturing, value stream mapping, production standardization, and single-

piece flow. This model also includes kanban, line balancing, the U-shaped line concept, quick changeover, and employee involvement (Sundar, Balaji, Kumar, 2014). Lean Manufacturing is a philosophy widely adopted in manufacturing systems worldwide, and the application of these principles enables gains in scale, reduction of losses, more precise control of operations, and a comprehensive mapping of the organization's value stream.

3. METHOD

This research is characterized as qualitative in nature and descriptive in purpose, developed through a case study. According to Gil (2022) and Denzin and Lincoln (2006), qualitative research adopts an interpretive perspective, in which the researcher seeks to understand phenomena through participants' experiences and meanings. This approach is appropriate for studying participatory dynamics in corporate environments, as it allows analysis of how individuals interact, learn, and assign meaning to practices encountered during training.

As highlighted by Marconi and Lakatos (2003), descriptive research within a qualitative approach enables the description, analysis, and interpretation of social phenomena, revealing patterns and characteristics relevant to understanding the context.

According to Gil (2019) and Yin (2015), a case study is an in-depth investigation of one or a few cases, allowing for a detailed understanding of real-life situations. This strategy is particularly useful for analyzing complex phenomena in their context, facilitating description, hypothesis formulation, and understanding variables that are difficult to explain through surveys or experiments.

In the present study, this approach enables exploration of the use of participatory dynamics in corporate training while preserving the context's uniqueness. The choice of this design is justified by the need to understand how the use of participatory dynamics in corporate training can contribute to the development of professional competencies, given the

specific reality of the analyzed organization. Data collection for this study was conducted in a metal-mechanical company located in the Serra Gaúcha region during the second half of 2024.

The operations area is responsible for leading continuous improvement initiatives through projects on production lines, using Lean Manufacturing principles to optimize results and increase operational efficiency. After completion of improvement projects, the responsible area conducts training sessions with production operators to contextualize the changes resulting from the implemented actions. At this stage, the main concepts of Lean Manufacturing are presented, and an interactive activity is conducted in which operators simulate a cardboard box production line, experiencing in practice the procedures and workflows that have been planned.

Data collection was conducted through direct observation and interaction with operators during the training sessions to understand how they absorbed the content and applied the new knowledge in the workplace. In addition to monitoring engagement and participation in the proposed activities, we observed improvements in production line performance.

The training sessions initially followed a traditional methodology, conducted in a training room organized as shown in Figure 1, based on expository and dialogic lectures. However, the results obtained did not meet expectations, as low knowledge retention, limited interest, and high levels of distraction among operators were observed. Given this scenario, it became necessary to adopt a new approach, which led to the implementation of interactive training sessions.

Figure 1 – Training Room

The study sample comprised 8 training groups, each with 16 participants, for a total of 128 operators from a population of 1,150.

These groups were distributed across the company's two shifts to accommodate different schedules and production routines. The study was conducted with participants of both genders, aged 18 to 65, including both early-career individuals and more experienced professionals. The sample also included participants of different nationalities and varying educational backgrounds. It is worth noting that two of these groups were dedicated to refresher training, aimed at reinforcing and updating the knowledge of operators who had previously participated in training programs.

The development of this study encountered some limitations. One of them refers to the use of data and images, as the company where the research was conducted did not authorize their disclosure, which restricted the presentation of certain elements. Additionally, factors

such as the availability of adequate physical space for conducting the training sessions and the time allocated by the organization for operators to participate in the activities also constituted limiting factors.

3.1 Training Description

The company's Operations department is responsible for developing continuous improvement projects by applying Lean Manufacturing principles to production lines. At the end of each project, training is provided to operators who work directly on the line affected by the changes, with the objective of presenting the implemented modifications and promoting an understanding of the principles that guided the improvements.

This training moment is not limited to the transmission of information but seeks to actively engage operators in the learning process. To this end, the training combines the presentation of key Lean Manufacturing concepts with dynamic, interactive activities that simulate a production line by assembling cardboard boxes. This interactive approach facilitates content assimilation, stimulates critical reflection on processes, and contributes to the development of technical and behavioral competencies essential for consolidating a culture of continuous improvement.

The training is conducted in a dedicated room, separate from the production environment, in order to promote concentration and minimize distractions. This strategy aims to create a learning-conducive environment that allows operators to temporarily step away from their work routines and focus fully on the proposed activities.

The training is titled "Box Game," and its main objective is to simulate a cardboard box production line. Figure 2 illustrates the organization of the training.

Figure 2: Box Game

In the image, the training is organized into four main stages. In item 1, the materials required to execute the activity are listed, including cardboard boxes, tables, a stopwatch, paper clips, and rubber bands. Item 2 illustrates how the room layout should be structured, arranging the tables to simulate a production line. In item 3, each operator is assigned a specific role, ensuring that all participants actively engage and interact during the activity. Finally, item 4 depicts the execution of the training, in which operators assume their positions and perform the assigned tasks, reproducing, in a controlled environment, a cardboard box assembly line.

The training begins with the presentation of a collective goal to the group: to produce 20 large assembled cardboard boxes within 5 minutes. Each large box must contain a small box with a paper clip inside and be finished with a rubber band on the outside. The supplier is responsible for providing the necessary materials to both the large box assembler and the

small box assembler; however, materials can only be supplied in batches of three units. This rule applies to all roles, as each participant can only proceed to the next stage after completing 3 units. The timekeeper is responsible for controlling the duration of each individual activity so that this information can be used later.

After the instructions are given, the activity begins with the countdown of the established 5-minute period. The supplier delivers the materials to the assemblers, while the other operators eagerly await their tasks. Difficulties arise in assembling the large boxes, delaying the progression of the stages and consequently generating demotivation among the team, which ultimately fails to meet the target within the allotted time.

During the first round, operators express frustration and state that the established goal is impossible to achieve. At this point, the group gathers to receive introductory explanations of Lean Manufacturing concepts, establishing a direct connection between the activity and the company's production line reality. Based on these reflections, participants are encouraged to collaboratively propose possible improvements to the process. A new round of training is then initiated, incorporating the suggestions collectively developed.

In this first round, the main objective is to develop competencies such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and teamwork. Additionally, operators begin to exercise their ability to adapt to seemingly unattainable challenges. Figure 3 shows the operators during the training session.

Figure 3: Operators in Training

In the second round, as operators implement the improvements discussed, they begin working in a more organized and collaborative manner. This shift fosters the development of competencies such as teamwork, effective communication, attention to detail, and adaptability, which were the objectives of this stage. Through this experience, participants realize how small process changes can have a significant impact on results and enhance their professional skills.

Thus, participants experience firsthand how incremental improvements can influence performance outcomes and contribute to skill development. Although the operators come close to the initial target of 20 boxes, they are still unable to achieve it. Figure 4 presents a record captured during the execution of the activity.

Figure 4: Operators in Training, Stage 2

In the third round, the group comes together once again and receives new concepts that reinforce the importance of applying theory to practice. Based on these reflections, operators are encouraged to propose further changes to the activity and implement adjustments they believe will improve the process. Subsequently, the third round of training begins.

This time, the team achieved the established target, demonstrating that, through collaboration, critical analysis, and continuous improvement, it is possible to overcome challenges. This result practically reinforces the development of competencies such as planning, collective decision-making, and resilience in the face of difficulties.

At this stage, the focus is on consolidating competencies related to planning, collective decision-making, and resilience. It also aims to strengthen the ability to apply theory in

practice, demonstrating that, through collaboration and continuous improvement, it is possible to achieve concrete results and surpass targets previously considered unfeasible.

At the end of the activity, participants are invited to share feedback on how they felt during the experience. Most reported that, after the rounds, the production process became clearer and that they better understood the importance of organization, cooperation, and communication among team members. Additionally, they recognized that the practical experience helped them realize how small changes can lead to significant results.

This experience highlights the potential of interactive methodologies to promote not only the assimilation of technical concepts but also the development of behavioral and professional competencies.

4. RESULTS

The main outcome of this study was the development of a training manual based on the competencies observed during the implementation of the “Box Game” dynamic. This material was designed to integrate theory and practice, prioritizing operator interaction, engagement, and the continuous improvement of production processes. In addition, the findings enabled the development of a training plan (Appendix A) with potential for practical application in other organizations interested in replicating the methodology, allowing the model to be adapted to different organizational contexts and strengthening the use of interactive methodologies as a learning tool in industry.

The implementation of the “Box Game” training yielded significant results, demonstrating the effectiveness of the interactive methodology and its direct alignment with the objectives of this study. The Operations department began systematically monitoring production line indicators and observed that, even with predefined targets, operators achieved substantial performance gains, including increased productivity and reduced errors in the simulated process.

Beyond the quantitative results, improvements in operators' professional competencies were also observed. Notable developments included enhanced collaboration, effective communication, adaptability, and critical thinking—skills essential for consolidating a culture of continuous improvement. The dynamic also fostered the development of resilience and collective decision-making, competencies that directly impact operational efficiency and the ability to address real challenges in the production line.

Another relevant impact was the consolidation of practical learning. By simulating real work situations, operators clearly saw how small process changes can yield significant results, strengthening the connection between theory and practice. This experience reinforces that interactive methodologies not only facilitate the assimilation of technical concepts but also promote engagement, shared responsibility, and proactivity, aligning individual objectives with those of the organization.

Overall, the experience demonstrates that training extends beyond the immediate achievement of targets: it strengthens an organizational culture focused on continuous improvement, generates positive impacts on operational results, and contributes to strategic human development within the company, reinforcing the value of investing in training and applying Lean Manufacturing principles.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This study demonstrated that adopting interactive methodologies in corporate training is an effective strategy for developing professional competencies and strengthening both individual and collective performance. The applied dynamic, titled “Box Game,” demonstrated that combining theory and practice enables operators to understand Lean Manufacturing concepts and apply them in situations that simulate the realities of the production line.

Regarding the objectives proposed in this study, and with the aim of contributing to and disseminating the use of interactive methodologies in corporate training, the main objective—namely, the development of a training plan accompanied by a methodological guide—was fully achieved, enabling its application in different organizations interested in replicating the experience. This material is structured around the competencies developed during the “Box Game” dynamic and aims to provide a practical training framework that integrates theory and practice, promoting engagement, shared responsibility, and continuous improvement in organizational processes.

The results obtained indicate gains in terms of productivity, collaboration, communication, critical thinking, resilience, and collective decision-making, confirming that practical learning is a central element in consolidating a culture of continuous improvement. Furthermore, the experience provided participants with a clear perception of how small process changes can generate significant impacts on results, highlighting the importance of engagement, organization, and cooperation among team members.

The analysis of this study also reinforces the idea that traditional training approaches, focused solely on content delivery, have limitations in knowledge retention and operator motivation, particularly with adult learners. On the other hand, methodologies that encourage active participation and critical reflection enable not only the assimilation of technical concepts but also the development of behavioral and professional competencies, which are essential for adapting to dynamic and challenging environments.

The research demonstrates that investing in interactive training represents an opportunity to leverage organizational competitive advantage by integrating learning, engagement, and operational results. The study also contributes to academic literature by highlighting the applicability of participatory methods in developing professional competencies and reinforcing the relevance of innovative pedagogical practices in the corporate context.

Finally, it can be concluded that participatory dynamics constitute a powerful learning tool capable of aligning individual and organizational objectives, consolidating a culture of continuous improvement, and strengthening teams' adaptability in the face of market challenges. This study, therefore, reinforces the importance of rethinking training models and prioritizing approaches that promote active learning, engagement, and the practical application of acquired knowledge.

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Recebido em: 12/04/2026

Aprovado em: 14/05/2026

Publicado em: 06/06/2026

**Revista *OWL Journal*, Campina Grande - PB, v. 4 n. 6 (2026) - DOSSIÊ ESPECIAL:
Conhecimento, Formação e Transformação Social**

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